

Preparation and Characterisation of Tellurate Complex of Nickel(IV)

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It has been observed that small size, high positive charge and stability to take tetrahedral and octahedral geometry with oxygen are the main characteristics of heteropoly addenda. Te^{VI} ion satisfies all these characteristics. Therefore Te^{VI} ion can function as an interesting heteropoly addendum like iodine(VII) ion, as tellurate ion TeO_6^{6-} is a good oxidising as well as stabilising agent and can stabilise in some instances the unusual oxidation states of many transition metal ions similar to those of periodate ion, IO_6^{5-} .

Results and Discussion

In thermal analysis, the first weight-loss at 30–140° indicates the loss of loosely bound water of crystallisation, the second weight-loss at 140–375° corresponds to the loss of three molecules of water with the formation of an intermediate compound, $\text{Li}_2\text{NiTe}_6\text{O}_{21}$. The DTA peak at 580° shows the decomposition with the formation of Li_2O , NiO and TeO_2 .

The infrared spectra for the compound showed a broad band at 3 700–3 100 cm^{-1} (Te–OH) probably with the overlapping of the ν_{OH} of the lattice water. The band at 2 300 cm^{-1} (appeared at 2 320 and 2 280 cm^{-1} in case of telluric acid) is in agreement with that of the first harmonic of Te–OH deformation band at 1 200 cm^{-1} . The bands at 1 625 cm^{-1} (OH deformation of the water molecule) is practically absent in case of telluric acid. The bands at 1 160, 1 140 and 1 100 cm^{-1} are due to Te–OH deformation modes, which appear at higher frequency because of the stronger Te–O–H.....O–Te hydrogen bonding¹. IR spectra of the monoclinic form of the acid $\text{Te}(\text{OH})_6$ and the salt $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_4\text{TeO}_6$ are similar to this compound and confirm that the tellurium ion is hexacoordinated in the present compound^{1,2}. The peaks appearing at 700 and 630 cm^{-1} (Te–O valence stretching vibrations) are absent in free telluric acid³. The band at 430 cm^{-1} can be assigned to O–Te–O deformation vibrations at 260, 240 and 220 cm^{-1} may be expected due to the lattice vibrations⁴ of the present compound ($\text{Li}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$).

Magnetic moment : In this compound tetravalent nickel is a d^6 -system having the configuration $3d^24s4p^3$, i.e. no unpaired electron is present in the d -orbital of Ni^{IV} species. So the compound should be diamagnetic. But the effective magnetic moment value of the compound ($\text{Li}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was found to be 1.18 B.M., indicating that the present Ni^{IV} compound is weakly

paramagnetic. The magnetic moment value is rather high for a Ni^{IV} species either for temperature-independent paramagnetism⁵ or due to the presence of slight amount of Ni^{III} ions which have occupied some Ni^{IV} sites in the crystal lattices⁶.

Reflectance spectra : The compound did not have sufficient solubility in water, so the electronic spectrum was recorded with deep brown mother liquor in KOH. The spectrum of the present Ni^{IV} compound revealed a shoulder with high extinction at 23 256 and a sharp peak at 43 478 cm^{-1} . The band in the visible region may be assigned to a transition involving charge transfer from metal t_{2g} orbital to ligand orbital^{7,8}. The band at 43 478 cm^{-1} is a charge transfer band, characteristic of TeO_6 octahedra³. The band in the visible region is consistent with octahedral coordination of the hetero ion⁹. Thus electronic spectrum establishes octahedral geometry around both nickel and tellurium ions and as such the intense brown colour of the compound may be due to some sort of covalent interaction in between them resulting in the distortion of the overall octahedral geometry. The diffused reflectance and the electronic spectra of the compound are identical, which indicates that the species $[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6]^{2-}$ is present in solid as well as in solution states³.

Potentiometric titration : The potentiometric titration of $\text{Li}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with standard Na_2SO_3 solution showed an inflection point at 0.650 V vs SCE. The volume (2.1 ml) of Na_2SO_3 solution (0.1364 N) required at this inflection point corresponds to 0.0002864 equivalent of the complex which indicates that both the Ni^{4+} and TeO_6^{6-} ions are completely reduced to Ni^{2+} and TeO_3^{2-} . The theoretical calculation shows that the reduction of 1 g-mol of $\text{Li}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires 7 g-mol of Na_2SO_3 solution. The results are given (Table 1) together with the published data.

TABLE I			
System	E_0 V	Ref	
$\text{Ni}(\text{IO}_4)_6^{2-} / \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{I}$	0.38	7	
$[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6)_2(\text{OH})_2]^{4-} / \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{IO}_3^-$	0.69	10	
$\text{Ni}(\text{L})^{2+} + 2e + 2\text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2+}$	0.70 ± 0.01	11	
$\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6 / \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{TeO}_3^{2-}$	0.65		

The experimental result is in excellent agreement with the theoretical values and the process of reduction may be represented by the equation.

The potential value (i.e. 0.650 V) vs SCE may be regarded as the standard potential for $[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6]^{2-}/\text{Ni}^{2+}$, TeO_3^{2-} system, which indicates that $[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6]^{2-}$ is a strong oxidant.

X-Ray studies : Single crystal of the compound was not formed. The X-ray powdered photograph of the compound was taken in a Guineer camera using CuK_α radiation. The interplanar d -spacings (\AA) were calculated as 3.601, 3.352, 2.842, 2.504 and 2.361, which indicates that the compound is crystalline in nature.

Experimental

Ni complex¹² : A mixture of nickel(II) nitrate (0.5 g) and telluric acid (0.5 g), both dissolved in water (30 ml), was heated at 80° and then hot 6*N* KOH solution (50 ml) was added with constant stirring at 80°. Solid potassium persulphate was then added to it in three or four portions maintaining the same temperature and stirring continuously for 0.5 h. The resulting deep brown solution was filtered, kept on an ice-bath and filtered again to discard the crystalline precipitates. To the filtrate, equivalent amount of lithium sulphate was added and the resulting brown solid was washed with a small amount of cold water and several times with alcohol-water (1 : 1) mixture and dried over fused CaCl_2 .

Tellurium was estimated gravimetrically by Hornberger method¹³. The filtrate and washings remaining after the removal of metallic tellurium were collected to estimate Ni gravimetrically by precipitating as $\text{Ni}(\text{DMGH})_2$ in neutral medium¹⁴. Lithium was estimated by atomic absorption spectroscopy using a Varian Techtron AA6 spectrometer. Water was computed from the weight-loss of the compound from the TGA curve.

The compound had the formula $\text{Li}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{HTeO}_4)_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Found : Li, 1.01; Ni, 4.61; Te, 59.9; H_2O , 3.00. Calcd. for : Li, 1.028; Ni, 4.643; Te, 60.560; H_2O , 2.847%). Equivalent weight of the compound determined by iodometric method was found to be 90.86 (calcd. 90.30) according to the reaction,

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 357 spectrophotometer and reflectance spectra on a Cary 17D spectrophotometer using magnesium carbonate as absorbent. Thermal studies (TGA and DTA) were carried out with a Stanton-Redcroft (London) TG 750 instrument at the rate of 10° per min in static air.

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References

1. N. E. ERICKSON and A. G. MADDOCK, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 1665.
2. H. SIEBERT, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1959, **301**, 161.
3. A. BALIKUNGERI, M. PELLETIER and D. MOUNIER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1977, **22**, 7.
4. R. A. NYQUIST and R. O. KAGEL, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic Compounds (3800-45 cm^{-1})", Academic, New York, 1973, p. 319.
5. P. RAY and B. SARMA, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **25**, 205; R. L. CARLIN and A. J. DUYNVELDT, "Magnetic Properties of Transition Metal Compounds", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1977, p. 20.
6. K. NAG, M. CHOUDHURY, A. ROY and B. P. GHOSH, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1980, **35**, 1201.
7. L. C. W. BAKER, H. G. MUKHERJEE, S. B. SARKAR and B. K. CHOUDHURY, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 618.
8. C. J. NYMAN and R. A. PLANE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2617.
9. C. M. GLYNN, JR. and G. D. STUCKY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 333.
10. H. G. MUKHERJEE, B. MONDAL and S. DE, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 426.
11. J. G. MOHANTY, R. P. SINGH, A. N. SINGH and A. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 219.
12. L. JENSOVSKY, *Omagi Raluca Ripan*, 1966, 293 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, **67**, 60455); M. J. M. CAMPBELL and C. J. NYMAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 842.
13. A. W. HORNBERGER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 387.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans Green, London, 1961, p. 479.